

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature and Culture Research

كتاب المتون الكاملة للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية

Editörler - المحررون - Editors

Sami Baskın, Gehan M. Anwar Deeb, Muhammad Matarneh

04-08 Kasım/November 2025 - Antalya/Türkiye

ISBN: 978-625-92747-0-6

Yayımlanma Tarihi (Publishing Date): 30.11.2025

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Kapak Resmi:

KÜTÜPHANE BİLGİ KARTI

1. Basım, Elektronik Kitap (Çevrim içi / Web tabanlı)

210 x 297 mm

Kaynakça var, dizin yok.

ISBN 978-625-92747-0-6

1. Dil Bilimi 2. Edebiyat 3. Kültür Araştırmaları

PDF yayın

Yayımlanma adresi: <https://saybildercongress.com/dekak/>

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ÖN SÖZ

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 04–08 Kasım 2025 tarihleri arasında Türkiye'nin Antalya kentinde gerçekleştirilmiş; dil, edebiyat ve kültür alanlarını disiplinlerarası bir bakış açısıyla ele alan önemli bir bilimsel buluşma platformu olmuştur. Kongre, Saybiller Topluluğu organizasyonunda; başta Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage University (Tunus) olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının akademik desteğiyle düzenlenmiştir.

Kongre kapsamında, farklı akademik gelenekleri ve araştırma perspektiflerini temsil eden 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı bilim insanlarıyla buluşturulmuştur. Ayrıca Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça dillerinde yapılan çağrılarla geniş bir uluslararası katılım sağlanmıştır. Bu çok dilli ve kapsayıcı çağrı süreci sonucunda gönderilen bildiriler, bilimsel etik ve kalite ilkeleri doğrultusunda hakem değerlendirme sürecinden geçirilmiştir. Yapılan değerlendirmeler neticesinde Türkiye'den 34, Türkiye dışından ise Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Katar, Kuveyt, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı ve Ürdün olmak üzere 13 farklı ülkeden 114 bildiri, kongre programında yer almış; böylece toplam 148 bildiri bilim dünyasıyla paylaşılmıştır.

Bu kongre kitabında yer alan çalışmalar; dil, edebiyat ve kültür araştırmalarında güncel kuramsal yaklaşımları, özgün analizleri ve farklı coğrafyalardan gelen akademik deneyimleri bir araya getirmektedir. Kongre süreci, özellikle uluslararası ve kültürlerarası iş birliğine dayalı araştırmaların bilimsel bilginin evrenselleşmesi ve akademik etkileşimin sürdürülebilirliği açısından taşıdığı önemi bir kez daha ortaya koymuştur.

Bu bağlamda araştırmacıların; disiplinlerarası çalışmalara daha fazla yönelmeleri, ortak projeler ve çok yazarlı uluslararası yayınlar aracılığıyla akademik etkileşimi güçlendirmeleri ve farklı dillerde bilimsel üretim yaparak çalışmalarının görünürlüğünü artırmaları önem arz etmektedir. Üniversitelerin, araştırma merkezlerinin ve diğer paydaşların ise genç araştırmacıları destekleyen, uluslararası akademik ağları teşvik eden ve nitelikli bilimsel üretimi sürdürülebilir kılan yapılar oluşturmaya devam etmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu kongrenin ve elinizdeki kitabın; alan yazınına anlamlı katkılar sunmasını, yeni akademik iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamasını ve dil, edebiyat ile kültür araştırmalarında nitelikli bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmesini temenni eder; kongrenin gerçekleştirilmesinde emeği geçen tüm kurumlara, hakemlere, davetli konuşmacılara ve değerli araştırmacılara teşekkür ederiz.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

PREFACE

The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research, held in Antalya, Türkiye, between November 4–8, 2025, constituted a significant academic platform that brought together studies in language, literature, and culture within an interdisciplinary framework. The congress was organized by the Saybilder Community, with the academic support of several higher education institutions, most notably Mardin Artuklu University and Carthage University.

Within the scope of the congress, invited speakers from six different countries met with scholars representing diverse academic traditions and research perspectives. In addition, calls for papers were announced in Turkish, English, and Arabic, enabling broad international participation. Following these multilingual calls, the submitted papers underwent a peer-review process conducted in accordance with scientific and ethical standards. As a result of the evaluations, a total of 148 papers were included in the scientific program, comprising 34 papers from Türkiye and 114 papers from 13 different countries, namely the United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Indonesia, Morocco, Palestine, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Kuwait, Egypt, Syria, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.

The studies presented in this proceedings book brought together contemporary theoretical approaches, original analyses, and diverse academic experiences from different geographical regions in the fields of language, literature, and culture. In particular, the congress clearly demonstrated the importance of international and intercultural collaborative research, emphasizing its crucial role in the universal dissemination of scientific knowledge and the establishment of sustainable interaction among different academic traditions.

In this context, researchers are encouraged to further engage in interdisciplinary studies, to strengthen academic interaction through joint projects and international co-authored publications, and to enhance the visibility of their research by producing scholarly work in multiple languages. Universities, research centers, and other stakeholders are likewise encouraged to continue supporting early-career researchers, fostering international academic networks, and developing sustainable structures for high-quality scientific production.

It is our sincere hope that this congress and the present proceedings book will contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, inspire new academic collaborations, and promote rigorous scientific research in the fields of language, literature, and cultural studies. We would like to express our gratitude to all institutions, reviewers, invited speakers, and distinguished researchers who contributed to the successful realization of this congress.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

انعقد المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغة والأدب والدراسات الثقافية في مدينة أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، وشكّل منصة علمية متميزة جمعت دراسات اللغة والأدب والثقافة في إطارٍ متعدد التخصصات. وقد نُظِم المؤتمر من قِبَل مجتمع سايبيلدر (Saybilder)، بدعمٍ علمي من عدد من مؤسسات التعليم العالي، وفي مقدمتها جامعة ماردين أرتقلو وجامعة قرطاج (Carthage University).

وشهد المؤتمر مشاركة متحدثين مدعويين من ست دول مختلفة، حيث التقى هؤلاء بنخبة من الباحثين الذين يمثلون مدارس أكاديمية ورؤى بحثية متنوعة. كما أُطلقت دعوات المشاركة باللغات التركية والإنجليزية والعربية، ما أسهم في تحقيق مشاركة دولية واسعة. وبعد ذلك، خضعت البحوث المقدّمة لعملية تحكيم علمي وفق المعايير الأكاديمية والأخلاقية المعتمدة. وأسفرت هذه العملية عن إدراج 148 بحثاً ضمن البرنامج العلمي، منها 34 بحثاً من تركيا و 114 بحثاً من 13 دولة هي: الإمارات العربية المتحدة، الجزائر، إندونيسيا، المغرب، فلسطين، العراق، إيران، قطر، الكويت، مصر، سوريا، المملكة العربية السعودية، والأردن.

وقد جمعت الدراسات الواردة في هذا الكتاب بين أحدث المقاربات النظرية، والتحليلات الأصيلة، والتجارب الأكاديمية المتنوعة من مختلف المناطق الجغرافية في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة. كما أبرز المؤتمر بوضوح أهمية البحوث القائمة على التعاون الدولي والتفاعل الثقافي، لما لها من دور محوري في تعميم المعرفة العلمية وبناء تفاعل أكاديمي مستدام بين التقاليد العلمية المختلفة.

وانطلاقاً من نتائج هذا اللقاء العلمي، يُشجّع الباحثون على توسيع نطاق الدراسات البيئية، وتعزيز المشاريع المشتركة، والإسهام في النشر العلمي الدولي المشترك، إضافة إلى الإنتاج البحثي متعدد اللغات بما يزيد من انتشار الأبحاث وتأثيرها. كما تُدعى الجامعات ومراكز البحث وسائر الشركاء الأكاديميين إلى مواصلة دعم الباحثين الشباب، وتعزيز الشبكات العلمية الدولية، وبناء هياكل مستدامة تضمن جودة واستمرارية الإنتاج العلمي.

وإذ نأمل أن يكون هذا المؤتمر وهذا الكتاب قد أسهما في إثراء الأدبيات العلمية وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، فإننا نتقدم بخالص الشكر والتقدير إلى جميع المؤسسات المشاركة، والمحكمين، والمتحدثين المدعويين، والباحثين الكرام الذين أسهموا في إنجاح هذا الحدث العلمي.

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Konu : Görevlendirme Hakkında (Prof.Dr.
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Functional Study of the Arabic Translation of Samuel Taylor Coleridge's *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner*: Artificial Intelligence Versus Human Intelligence in Literary Translation

Dina Ahmed Abdel Aziz Ramadan, PhD

Department of English Language and Literature, Faculty of Women for Arts, Science and Education,
Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

Abstract

This paper investigates the Arabic translation of Samuel Taylor Coleridge's *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner* by an AI translation application QuillBot and another one by AbdulWahab Elmessiri as an example of human literary translation. In his translation, Elmessiri tried to preserve the aesthetics of poetic language. The cultural knowledge of Elmessiri is reflected in the accuracy of choice of words and expressions in his human translation. On the other hand, the QuillBot translation is accurate, fast, and concise, but it does not reflect the essence and the intended meaning of the literary text as much as the human translation does. This study compares and contrasts the two Arabic translations of *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner*, namely, the AI and human translations using the framework of functional translation theory, first known as Skopos theory. "Skopos" is a Greek word meaning "purpose" or "function". In functional translation theory, the main concern is the function of the source and target texts. The approach of Skopos theory being applied in this study is Nord's 2005 approach that adds loyalty to the purpose of the source and target texts. Findings of the study show how artificial intelligence translation lacks cultural sensitivity and deep understanding of the source text and hence does not achieve the function of literary translation appropriately. Human intelligence, in contrast, shows profound understanding of the source text and transfers cultural nuances and poetic aesthetics in the target text achieving the purpose of literary translation properly.

Keywords: The Rime of the Ancient Mariner, functional translation theory, Skopos theory, artificial intelligence, human intelligence, literary translation, translation and cultural exchange

Introduction

By the development of AI tools, many fears and questions concerning the role of human being emerge; will AI technology replace human beings in many fields? Can AI function adequately playing the role of humans? As for translation in general and literary translation in particular, AI tools provide a fast, accurate, and professional translation that could compete with human translation in regards to linguistic strict equivalence. Functional theories of translation focus on the function of the source text (ST) and to what extent this function is achieved through the process of translation in the target text (TT).

This study compares and contrasts samples of the Arabic translation of Samuel Taylor Coleridge's *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner* by an AI translation tool, namely QuillBot application, and by the Egyptian intellectual Abdulwahab Elmessiri. Quillbot application is a free online AI-powered tool that instantly translates texts into more than 50 languages. Quillbot is fast, accurate, and user friendly. As for the selected poem *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner*, it is written in 1797-1799 by the English poet Samuel

Taylor Coleridge and published in the first edition of *Lyrical Ballads*. It is Coleridge's longest poem. It is written in seven parts and it marked the beginning of English Romantic literature. The poem is about a mariner who shoots an albatross, and got a supernatural curse by the death of his crew. He suffers profoundly and finds redemption only by learning to love all creatures. He is compelled to retell his haunting tale as self-punishment, teaching lessons of sin, guilt, and nature's sacredness (Nicolson, 2020).

The poem is translated into Arabic by the Egyptian intellectual Abdulwahab Elmessiri. It is published as a bilingual illustrated edition in 2007. The illustrations are drawn by the distinguished Egyptian artist Rabab Nemr. The book is designed by Helmi El-Touni, the Egyptian late artist. This poem along with its Arabic translation is selected to be analysed, since it is loaded with cultural nuances. The researcher seeks to depict the achievement of the function of AI translation versus human translation in delivering the intended message of the ST.

Functional theory of translation is selected as the framework of the study to analyse AI and human translations from a functional perspective. In other words, the analysis investigates whether the function of the ST is attained in the TT of both the AI and human translations or not. The functional translation theories have been developed in the early twentieth century in Germany (Zheng, 2017, p. 623).

In the following section, the development of the functional theory is presented in detail and translation studies applying the functional theories are mentioned briefly to show how the current study differs from the previous literature.

Literature Review

Zheng 2017 states that "Functionalist approaches to translation were developed in Germany by a number of German translators in the late 1970s." Before the development of functional theories of translation, the main focus was on word for word translation and linguistic equivalence. In other words, translation studies were linguistically oriented. Newmark 1998 asserts that translation was a code-switching operation. This linguistic approach to translation fails to cover many aspects in the process of translation such as cultural nuances, information transfer, and aesthetic effects. Thus a need for a new approach emerged. Naudé (2002) declares that:

From the 1980s, translation scholars began to view translation through social and political lenses. This shift coincided with the emergence of the "cultural turn" and the increasing interdisciplinary developments in the humanities and social sciences. (Naudé, 2002, p.44)

The cultural turn started to shift the focus of translation from the TT to extra-textual factors and cross-cultural perspectives. The target culture is emphasised in the mindset of translators. This paved the way for the functional approach to translation. The purpose of the translation started to be a priority in translation practice. Munday (2001) declares that in the 70s and 80s the functionalist and communicative approaches to translation flourished in Germany. The German scholars developed the Skopos theory. "Skopos" means function or purpose in Greek (Reiss & Vermeer 1984; Schäffner 1998a; Munday et al. 2022). The German scholars Hans J. Vermeer and Christiane Nord were pioneers in this perspective to translation practice. Vermeer (1989) views translation as an action and each action must have a purpose. He states basic rules for translation according to Skopos theory as follows:

1. The final version of the target text TT is determined by its purpose.
2. The role of the source text ST in the source culture may be different to the role of the TT in the target culture.
3. The translator should take into consideration the target audience's situation and knowledge background. In other words, the TT should be internally coherent.

4. The TT should have fidelity to the ST, i.e., coherent with the ST.

Du (2012) declares that:

In the framework of Skopos theory, there are not such things as right or wrong, faithfulness or unfaithfulness, and the translation Skopos decides the translation process. Skopos theory accounts for different strategies in different situations, in which the source text is not the only factor involved. (p.2190)

Du (2012) adds that Vermeer is the founder of the Skopos theory. Skopos theory's main concern is the purpose of translation which in turn determines the translation strategies to be used to produce the "functionally adequate result" (p. 2190)

Reiss (1971) based the starting point of translation analysis in Germany (Nord, 2001). Reiss (1971) claims that the best translation is one in which the aim in the TT is equivalence of the conceptual content, linguistic form and communicative function of a ST. But she finds out that equivalence is sometimes impossible. In order to fill in the gap between theory and practice, Vermeer founded the functional theory of translation, namely Skopos theory in 1978. Du (2012) states that "Vermeer thinks that to translate means to produce a text in a target setting for a target purpose and target addressees in target circumstances" (p.2191). In 1981, Holz-Manttari puts forward "Translational action" which is based on action theory. It covers all forms of intercultural transfer. Holz-Manttari (1981) defines translation as a complex action that should achieve a particular purpose. Nord (1997) extends the Skopos theory and she introduces the term "loyalty" as a crucial principle within the functional framework, confirming that the translator should respect the ST, the author's intentions and the target audience's expectations, balancing fidelity with functionality.

Ever since, functional purpose of translation becomes the focus of translational studies especially literary translation. In 2017, Jabak and Abdullah applied Skopos theory to the Arabic translation of Miller's *Death of a Salesman* by the Syrian translator Omar Jabak. The study reveals that Vermeer's version of Skopos theory has some drawbacks when applied to literary translation because of the social and cultural background of the target audience.

In 2021, Daud et al. conducted a study that applies Skopos theory in evaluation of readability and cohesion in Malay translation of four English children fables. The researchers found out that the translation procedures used created a cohesive translation, thus increasing readability of the stories for the TT, i.e. Malaysian children.

VanDemark (2022) applied Skopos theory to German literary translation. It is a project that translated a German short story "Ein neues Paradies" by Hans Dominik into modern American English following Skopos theory. The project proves that Skopos theory succeeds "in capturing cultural and historical elements of the story, but struggled to address literary and stylistic elements such as tone which can have complex and multiple purposes." (VanDenmark, 2022, p. 2)

Alsager and Almohizea (2023) analyze the Arabic subtitle translation of the film *Mulan* 2020 using the framework of Skopos theory. The study shows some translation violations on many linguistic levels in the light of Skopos theory. Moreover, "the findings suggest that the Skopos theory can be used as a tool to evaluate subtitle translation" (Alsager and Almohizea, 2023, p. 50).

Laratmase et al. (2025) explores the use of Skopos theory in translating children's literature with focus on how translation choices should be guided by purpose and context. Cultural understanding and alignment with the cognitive and emotional needs of children as the target audience are highlighted.

In this section, the development of Skopos theory is explained in detail, along with a brief overview of previous studies applying Skopos theory to translation studies in general and literary translation in

particular. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, the current study is the first study to compare and contrast AI and human literary translations in light of Skopos theory to investigate to what extent the AI translation reflects the cultural and aesthetic aspects of the selected text in comparison to the human translation of the same text within the framework of Nord's Skopos theory (1997, 2005).

Aim of the Study

This study aims to investigate the Arabic translation of Coleridge's *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner* by an AI application, namely, Quillbot and by the Egyptian intellectual Abdulwahab Elmessiri as an example of human translation. The investigation of the translations is conducted within the framework of Skopos theory by Nord 2005 in order to depict the advantages and disadvantages of utilizing AI in literary translation in comparison to human translation in order to see how cultural nuances and aesthetics of poetry could be transferred in the examined translations.

Research Questions

How do AI and human translations differ in their rendition of the poem's archaic language, intricate rhyme scheme, and metrical structure into Arabic?

To what extent can AI translation replicate the tonal nuances, prosody, and stylistic integrity achieved by human translation?

How effectively do AI and human translations convey the cultural references, symbolism (e.g., the albatross), and themes (e.g., guilt, redemption, nature) in a manner that resonates with an Arabic-speaking audience?

How do the differences in translation approach (AI vs. human) impact the overall effectiveness of the translation in engaging the target audience and fulfilling its literary function?

What are the key advantages and limitations of AI translation technologies in the context of translating complex Romantic English poetry into Arabic, and can they potentially complement human translators in this specific domain?

The Theoretical Framework

As declared in the literature review section above, Skopos theory goes beyond traditional concerns with equivalence and faithfulness between ST and its TT, providing a broader framework that gives priority to the intended function of the translation (VanDemark 2022).

Nord's framework (2005) adapts Skopos theory (purpose-driven translation) for literature by emphasizing the function of TT while integrating the loyalty principle acknowledging translator responsibility to both source ST and TT audience, crucial for complex literary texts often lacking one clear purpose. She also stresses the coherence rule ensuring the TT makes sense in its target context, and differentiates between text types, proposing strategies like domestication/foreignization based on the specific literary *skopos*, making translation a purposeful action rather than just linguistic equivalence.

Nord (2005) rejects word-for-word or effect-for-effect translation favoring functional appropriateness. She also recognizes literary texts have complex functions, sometimes requiring foreignization (preserving cultural distance) or domestication (making it familiar) depending on the *skopos*. Nord (2005) views the translator as a producer of a new text for a specific purpose, not just a conduit for the original author.

Nord's framework provides tools such as loyalty, text typology, and coherence to apply the dynamic, purpose-driven principles of Skopos theory effectively to the unique challenges of literary translation. She

states that “translation is normally expected to render “faithfully” all the relevant features of the source text.” (Nord, 2005, p.25). In addition, she declares that:

[a] translator who has to translate a literary text from another period in history, often has to resort to text-analytical methods in order to determine the conditions of its reception. In such a case, it may even be necessary to distinguish between the “original” reception in the author’s time and reception in the translator’s time. (Nord, 2005, p. 7)

She calls this process “intercultural text transfer” (p.7). Nord (2005) sums up this as follows: “Being culture-bound communicative signs, both the source and the target texts are determined by the communicative situation in which they serve to convey a message.” (p. 8). Nord (2005) states that:

. . . having grown up in another culture, the TT receiver has a different knowledge of the world, a different way of life, a different perspective on things, and a different “text experience” in the light of which the target text is read. (p. 28)

For this reason, Nord (2005) decides that functionality of translation is an important element, but it is not the only one. She states that there must be a relationship between the ST and TT. This relationship is determined by the translation skopos and specifies which elements of the ST in situation can be preserved and which can be adapted to the target situation (Nord, 2005).

Nord (2005) introduces the term “loyalty” and defines it as the responsibility of the translator towards the ST/sender and TT/receiver situation. She also differentiates between intratextual and extratextual factors affecting the translation process. Intratextual factors include the subject matter of the ST, its content, the knowledge presupposed by the author, the linguistic features like lexical, syntactic, and prosodic features. Extratextual factors include the sender/author, his/her intention, the audience/receiver, the medium the text is communicated by, the place, the time, and the motivation for writing the ST.

Nord (2005) states that:

. . . translation criticism should be based on a comparative analysis of both the source and the target text and should provide information about the similarities and differences of SL and TL structures represented in both texts, as well as about the individual process of translation and the strategies and methods used. It should also show whether the target text is appropriate for the required translation skopos. (p. 180)

This is exactly what is conducted in this current study. The researcher compares the ST and the TT by AI and human translators within the framework of the Skopos theory to examine if the TT is appropriate for the intended translation purpose. In the next section, the methodology, data collection and limitation of the study are explained.

Methodology, Data Collection and Limitation of the Study

The researcher selects parts of the ST of *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner* by Samuel Taylor Coleridge and compares these selections to their Arabic translations by the AI application Quillbot and Abdulwahab Elmessiri as an example of human translation. The excerpts of ST are processed by Quillbot to generate an AI-translated version. The selections and their translations are examined on different linguistic levels/intratextual factors, i.e. syntactic structures, lexical choices, and suprasegmental features of prosody and rhythm. The analysis also includes cultural appropriateness, accuracy, and handling of literary devices. It is a qualitative analysis. The study is limited to these two translations.

The Analysis of the AI and Human Translations

Before delving deeper into the analysis of the intratextual factors of the excerpts and their Arabic translations, the extratextual of both ST and TT are detailed as follows:

Extratextual Factors			
Sources Text		Target Text	
		AI	Human
Producer/sender	Samuel Taylor Coleridge	Quillbot	Abdulwahab Elmessiri
Time	1797-1799	Instant	2000-2006
Place	England	Online	Egypt
Intention	To convey a moral message for people to feel for God's creatures and appreciate nature	NA	To transfer the literary work to the Arab readers
Audience/Receiver	English people/readers of English literature	NA	Arabs
Medium	Poetry	Poetry	Poetry
Motive	Experimenting with new forms of poetry and narrative styles	NA	His fascination by the poem

The following excerpt is the first stanza from the opening of the poem:

Excerpt 1:

Source Text	Quillbot's Translation	Elmessiri's Translation
It is an ancient Mariner, And he stoppeth one of three. 'By thy long grey beard and glittering eye, Now wherefore stopp'st thou me?	إنه بحار قديم، وهو يوقف واحدًا من ثلاثة. 'بلحيتك الرمادية الطويلة وعينيك المتلألئتين، لماذا توقفت عني الآن؟	إنه ملاح قديم يستوقف واحدًا من ثلاثة. "لم تستوقفني الآن بحق لحيتك الرمادية الكثة، وعينك البراقة؟

It is noticed in the above translation that Quillbot kept the syntactic structure of sentences of ST, whereas, Elmessiri changed the syntactic structure by deleting "And" in line 2 and starting with the question in line 3. Quillbot used the word "بحار", but Elmessiri used "ملاح" to keep the effect of the archaic word "Mariner". Quillbot does not follow the rhyme scheme abcb of the ST, but Elmessiri preserved it. Quillbot kept the punctuation marks the same as the ST, whereas Elmessiri changed them a little bit to conform to TT syntactic structure. Both Quillbot and Elmessiri used opening quotation marks without closing ones preserving the style of the ST. Quillbot used single quotation marks (the same like the ST), whereas Elmessiri used double quotation marks to abide by Arabic language quotation marks double style.

Excerpt 2:

Source Text	Quillbot's Translation	Elmessiri's Translation
The Bridegroom's doors are opened wide, And I am next of kin; The guests are met, the feast is set: May'st hear the merry din.'	أبواب العريس مفتوحة على مصراعها، وأنا الأقرباء؛ الضيوف قد اجتمعوا، والوليمة قد أعدت: يمكنك سماع الضجيج المبهج.	أبواب دار العريس مفتوحة على مصراعها وأنا أقرب الأقربين إليه. لقد وصل الضيوف، وها هي ذي الموائد مُدَّت، وبوسعك أن تسمع الضجيج المرح.

In this excerpt, while Quillbot translates "The Bridegroom's doors" literally as "أبواب العريس", Elmessiri translates it as "أبواب دار العريس" to be understood by the Arab readers. Both Quillbot and Elmessiri translate the expression "opened wide" as "مفتوحة على مصراعها" which is a well-known Arabic expression. Again Quillbot preserves all the punctuation marks of the ST in the TT. "And I am the next of kin;" is translated by Quillbot as "وأنا الأقرباء;" which is a vague expression in Arabic, but as "وأنا أقرب الأقربين إليه." by Elmessiri which is a familiar expression in Arabic language. The syntactic structure of ST in the first two lines is preserved by both Quillbot and Elmessiri. In the third line, Elmessiri changes the word order to adhere to the Arabic language word order starting with the verb not the subject as is the case in the ST and Quillbot translation. The second part of the third line is in the passive voice and it is preserved in the TT by both. "the feast" is simply translated as "الوليمة" by Quillbot, but eloquently as "وها هي ذي الموائد" by Elmessiri. Finally, Elmessiri closes the stanza by the quotation marks that close the run on sentence starting by the quotation marks in the previous stanza, but Quillbot omitted the closing quotation marks, probably AI could not grasp the idea of having the quotation from a previous stanza (the researcher tried it more than one time including the previous stanza, but Quillbot omits the closing quotations marks every time). The rhyme scheme abcb of the ST is not preserved in either version.

Excerpt 3:

Source Text	Quillbot's Translation	Elmessiri's Translation
And through the drifts the snowy clifts Did send a dismal sheen: Nor shapes of men nor beasts we ken— The ice was all between.	ومن خلال الانجرافات أرسلت المنحدرات الثلجية بريقًا كثيبًا: لا أشكال للرجال ولا للوحوش نعرفها— كان الجليد هو كل ما بينهما.	ومن ثنايا الثلج الذي تذرره الرياح أرسلت الصخور الجليدية بريقًا مقبضًا، وحال الجليد بيننا وبين كل شيء، فلا رأينا إنسًا ولا وحشًا.

In this excerpt, Quillbot translates the lines literally and accurately. Quillbot does not conform here to the number of lines of the stanza in ST, instead it links the first two lines as one line. Elmessiri preserves the number of the lines in his TT. He uses a Qur'anic expression "تذرره الرياح" to give the lines a sense of familiarity, eloquence, and sacredness. Elmessiri changes the order of the last sentence by fronting of the forth line putting the cause before the result. Elmessiri also changes the punctuation marks of the ST in accordance with Arabic language rules. On the other hand, Quillbot sticks to the syntactic structure and punctuation marks of ST. The rhyme scheme of this stanza abcb is preserved by Elmessiri, but violated by Quillbot, since it changes the number of lines altogether.

Excerpt 4:

Source Text	Quillbot's Translation	Elmessiri's Translation
Ah! well a-day! what evil looks Had I from old and young! Instead of the cross, the Albatross About my neck was hung.	آه! يا للهول! ما شكل الشر لو كنت من الشيوخ والشباب! بدلاً من الصليب، كان الألباتروس معلقاً حول عنقي.	آه. واحسرتاه! أياه نظرات كريهة تلك التي سددها لي الكبير والصغير! وبدلاً من الصليب، في عنقي علقوا طائر القطرس الأبيض.

Quillbot in this excerpt shows less understanding of the stanza, since the sentence is a run-on one over two lines. "what evil looks/ Had I from old and young!" is translated by Elmessiri as "أية نظرات كريهة/ تلك التي" which delivers the intended meaning of the ST correctly. Elmessiri again uses the fronting technique in the last sentence putting "في عنقي" before "القطرس الأبيض". Elmessiri (2007) sees this as an allegory to the verse from the Holy Qur'an "وَكُلَّ إِنْسَانٍ أَلْزَمْنَاهُ طَائِرَهُ فِي عُنُقِهِ" (Al-Isra':13). The Mariner's sin of killing the albatross was hung around his neck and needs redemption to be released. Both Quillbot and Elmessiri preserved the punctuation marks of the ST except for the exclamation mark in "Ah!" is replaced by two dots by Elmessiri. The rhyme scheme abab is not preserved by both Quillbot and Elmessiri.

Excerpt 5:

Source Text	Quillbot's Translation	Elmessiri's Translation
O happy living things! no tongue Their beauty might declare: A spring of love gushed from my heart, And I blessed them unaware: Sure my kind saint took pity on me, And I blessed them unaware.	يا كائنات سعيدة! لا لسان قد تعلن جمالهن: ينابيع الحب تدفقت من قلبي، وباركتهن دون أن أدري: بالتأكيد أن قديسي الطيب قد شفقوا عليّ، وباركتهن دون أن أدري.	يا للكائنات الحية السعيدة! ما من لسان يمكن أن يحيط بحسنها وصفًا! انبتق في قلبي ينبوع من الحب، وباركته دون أن أدري. يقينًا. إن قديسي الرحيم قد أشفق عليّ، فباركته دون أن أدري!

In this excerpt, Quillbot translates the first sentence literally without transferring aesthetics of the poetic expression. Elmessiri, on the other hand borrowed a Qur'anic style in the expression "يحيط بحسنها وصفًا!" like in "مَا لَمْ نُحِظْ بِهِ خُبْرًا" (Al-Kahf: 68). The third line, both Quillbot and Elmessiri, translates it eloquently preserving the poetic aesthetics. Quillbot has a subject verb agreement mistake in the fifth line reflecting lack of understanding "قديسي الطيب قد شفقوا عليّ". Again the rhyme scheme of the ST is violated in both translations in favour of accuracy by Quillbot and poetic style by Elmessiri.

Excerpt 6:

Source Text	Quillbot's Translation	Elmessiri's Translation
This seraph-band, each waved his hand, No voice did they impart-- No voice; but oh! the silence sank Like music on my heart.	هذه الفرقة الملائكية، كل واحد منهم لوح بيده، لم ينطقوا بصوت-- لا صوت؛ ولكن أوه! لقد غاص الصمت مثل الموسيقى في قلبي.	زمرة الملائكة هذه، كل يحرك يده، ولم يصدر أي منها صوتًا. أطبق الصمت على كل شيء . . أطبق الصمت، لكن . . رباه، كالموسيقى، غاص الصمت في قلبي!

"Seraph-band" is translated literally by Quillbot as "الفرقة الملائكية", whereas Elmessiri uses "زمرة الملائكة" which is more poetic. The eloquence of Elmessiri's translation is in the choice of expressions like "أطبق" "الصمت على كل شيء" as opposed to "لم ينطقوا بصوت" by Quillbot. "but oh" is literally translated by Quillbot as "لكن أوه", but as "لكن . . رباه" by Elmessiri to adapt it to the Arabic context. Elmessiri fronted the word music in the last line, but Quillbot preserved the ST word order. The rhyme scheme abcb is not followed by either.

Excerpt 7:

Source Text	Quillbot's Translation	Elmessiri's Translation
He prayeth best, who loveth best All things both great and small; For the dear God who loveth us, He made and loveth all.	أفضل من يصلي، من يحب أفضل كل الأشياء الكبيرة والصغيرة؛ لأن الإله العزيز الذي يحبنا، هو الذي خلق ويحب الجميع.	خير من يصلي هو خير من يحب كل الأشياء، جليلها ودقيقها، لأن الإله العزيز الذي يحبنا خلق الكل وأحبهم.

The moral lesson of the poem is summarized in this last excerpt. The first two lines are translated literally by Quillbot, but Elmessiri as usual tries to transfer the spirituality of the ST by imitating religious texts "خير من يصلي هو خير من يحب". The third line is translated exactly the same by both. The last line is concisely translated as "خلق الكل وأحبهم" by Elmessiri, but word for word by Quillbot. The rhyme scheme again could not be followed by either.

Results and Discussion

The results of this study show how AI translates literary texts using word-for word strategy instead of trying to make the language as refined as an Arabic work of art. Both AI and human translators has loyalty to the ST in accurately delivering the meaning, but AI sometimes shows lack of understanding. Previous studies using Skopos theory as a framework of analysis compares the ST to the TT by human translators. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, this is the first study to compare and contrast human translation to AI translation within the framework of Skopos theory.

Throughout the study, there are four items examined in the selected lines, namely, syntactic structure, choice of words, prosody and aesthetics of poetry. The function of this poem is to experiment a new type of poetry full of spirituality, mystery, narration, and respect to nature. The religious tone of the poem is better reflected by Elmessiri who has a better understanding of religions and could achieve the purpose

of the ST appropriately using Qur'anic expressions and style. Elmessiri's deep understanding of both cultures enables him to flexibly adapt the text to the target culture by changing syntactic structure of sentences, replacing words, and refining sentences. Arabic readers can read his translation as a literary work that is originally written in Arabic. The music in the poem is also could be preserved to a great extent by Elmessiri who is a professor of English literature in general and poetry in particular. AI tries to be as accurate as possible, no matter what the intended message of the ST is, neglecting the aesthetics of poetry.

AI translates a run-on-sentence as separate sentences which distorts the meaning of the ST. Elmessiri shifts the order of the words using fronting to foreground certain words important to the intended meaning. Elmessiri is skillfully playing with words and expressions of the target language, since it is his mother tongue and the language he prefers to use in his writings. Artificial intelligence can get the meaning accurately, but not eloquently as the human intelligence can. AI surpasses human intelligence in the speed of translation as stated above, Elmessiri took around six years translating this work, but AI instantly translates a huge text.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Findings of the study can be summarized as follows: AI lacks the eloquence and cultural sensitivity of the human translation. AI is much concerned with literal translation and accuracy more than adaptability and domestication. Elmessiri's cultural knowledge helps him opt for the true meaning of the poem. Quillbot does not imitate the poem's archaic language as Elmessiri does. Quillbot neglects intricate rhyme scheme, and metrical structure altogether. Elmessiri tries to preserve music of poetry as much as he could.

It is apparent through the above analysis that Elmessiri's priority in translating this text is conveying cultural references, and religious tone and themes like guilt, redemption, and nature, in a manner that resonates with an Arabic-speaking audience.

The audience reading a literary text translated by a human translator are more engaged and affected by the real purpose of the ST than that translated by AI. AI can provide a tentative draft to the human translator that s/he can work on over and over to refine and adapt the text to the target language and culture. In other words, AI can assist humans in literary translation, but it can never replace humans in this specific domain. Maybe it can do so in other domains of translation, but this is beyond the scope of the current study.

More studies need to be conducted on the advantages and limitations of AI in translation of different works. The Arabic translation of *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner* and its illustrations by Rabab Nemr needs a multimodal analysis to see how drawing can depict meaning of the text.

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يمثل هذا الكتاب الإصدار العلمي الرسمي للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر لبحوث اللغة والأدب والثقافة، الذي عُقد في أطلاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من جمعية سايبيلدر وبالشراكة مع عدد من الجامعات والمؤسسات الأكاديمية في تركيا وتونس ودول أخرى. ويضم هذا العمل مجموعة منتقاة من الأبحاث المحكمة التي اجتازت مراحل المراجعة العلمية وفق معايير الجودة والأمانة الأكاديمية.

تعكس الدراسات الواردة في هذا المجلد التنوع المعرفي والغنى المنهجي في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة، كما تبرز قيمة التعاون العلمي الدولي من خلال مشاركة باحثين من ثلاث عشرة دولة. ويؤكد هذا الإصدار أهمية دعم الحراك البحثي متعدد التخصصات وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي بلغات مختلفة بما يعزز حضور المعرفة في فضاء البحث العالمي.

وإذ نقدّم هذا الكتاب إلى المجتمع الأكاديمي، نعبّر عن تقديرنا للجهات الداعمة والهيئات العلمية والمحكمين والباحثين المشاركين، آمليين أن يسهم هذا العمل في تعزيز الدراسات ذات الصلة وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي المستدام.

ISBN: 978-625-92747-0-6

